

3-Amino- and 3-Hydroxy- β -naphthapyrones.

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In a previous paper (Dey and Lakshminarayanan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 373) it has been shown that the action of alkali on 3-bromo-4-methyl- β -naphthapyrone gives rise to a product of a new type which is believed to be 2-hydroxynaphthyl-1- α -propionic aldehyde, in addition to the known β -naphthafuran carboxylic acid. To explain the formation of this extraordinary compound the suggestion was made that an intermediate 3-hydroxy- β -naphthapyrone was first formed and that the *cis* acid derived from the latter by the opening of the pyrone ring lost CO_2 and gave the aldehyde, thus:

As it seemed that our theory of the mechanism of this reaction could be tested by preparing, if possible, 3-hydroxy- β -naphthapyrones and studying their behaviour with alkalis, we undertook to carry out experiments in this direction and the results of some of these are described in the present communication. It may be stated at the outset that although the synthesis of the unsubstituted 3-hydroxy- β -naphthapyrone has now been accomplished, the treatment with alkali has not produced the desired aldehyde. We cannot definitely say, however, that this failure to obtain the aldehyde from 3-hydroxy- β -naphthapyrone invalidates our original hypothesis, since the methyl group in position 4 in the other naphthapyrone may have exercised an important influence, not taken into consideration in the present case, in determining the course of the change.

Erlenmeyer and Stadlin (*Annalen*, 1904, 337, 283) have studied the reaction between salicylaldehyde and hippuric acid and shown that a mixture of azlactone (I) and 3-benzoylamino coumarin (II) are formed thus:

We have investigated the same reaction with β -naphthol aldehyde and obtained 3-benzoylamino- β -naphthopyrone as the sole product of the reaction unmixed with any azlactone. The debenzoylation of this compound to the free amine was accomplished with a mixture of HBr and glacial acetic acid.

The amine formed a very sparingly soluble hydrochloride and an acetyl and a benzoyl derivative. The latter was identified with the product obtained directly from β -naphtholaldehyde and hippuric acid, while the former has been synthesised from β -naphtholaldehyde and glycine by a method similar to the one used by Linch (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 1766) for the preparation of 3-acetylamino coumarin thus:

The action of nitrous acid on the amine (III) leads to the formation of the desired 3-hydroxy- β -naphthapyrone (IV), the latter being also prepared in good yield through an unstable intermediate *cis* acid (V) by boiling the amine with alkali till the evolution of NH_3 had ceased:

All attempts to convert the *cis* acid into the expected 2-hydroxy-naphthyl acetaldehyde by decarboxylation were, however, fruitless.

We have compared the properties of 3-amino- β -naphthapyrone with those of 3-aminocoumarin prepared by Linch (*loc. cit.*) by the indirect method of subjecting 3-acetylcoumarin oxime (Knoevenagel, *Ber.*, 1889, 31, 732) to the Beckmann change.

Linch assumed that 3-aminocoumarin existed mainly in the tautomerised imino form on the ground that it yielded a nitroso- and a benzylidene derivative. 3-Amino- β -naphthapyrone behaved, however, in the normal manner and we have no grounds for assuming that the compound shows a tendency to tautomerise into the imino-form.

EXPERIMENTAL

3-Benzoylamino- β -naphthapyrone.—An intimate mixture of hippuric acid (6 g.), β -naphthol aldehyde (5.9 g.), anhydrous sodium acetate (2.9 g.) and acetic anhydride (12 g.) was heated to

100° for $\frac{3}{4}$ hour and the contents which changed to a hard orange mass on cooling, were broken up, treated with water and filtered. The insoluble matter was washed 6 times with 25 c. c. of ether when it became colourless and melted at 220-26° (5.2 g.). It was practically insoluble in alcohol and dissolved sparingly in glacial acetic acid from which it crystallised in silky needles, m.p. 130°, yield 4 g. The product was insoluble in cold acids or alkalis but on heating with the latter, it dissolved slowly with the evolution of ammonia. A solution of the substance in strong sulphuric acid exhibited a fine blue fluorescence. (Found: C, 76.11; H, 3.94; N, 4.34. $C_{20}H_{13}O_4N$ requires C, 76.19; H, 4.13; N, 4.44 per cent).

The ether washings from the above were dried over $CaCl_2$, the ether evaporated and the orange red oil distilled under reduced pressure. Two fractions were collected: (A), b.p. 132-140°/10 mm. which passed over as a light yellow oil and partly solidified and (B) b.p. 140-160°/10 mm. a colourless oil of a peculiar odour which gradually solidified to a crystalline mass. From (A) by fractional crystallisation from ether and from methanol, colourless needles (m.p. 120°) were finally obtained. These were identified as β -naphthapyrone by a mixed m.p. determination. On working up the mother liquor, a considerable amount of a second substance, m.p. 85°, were obtained which was identified as acetoxy- β -naphthol aldehyde. The crystals separating from fraction (B) crystallised from acetic acid in silky needles, m.p. 230° and were proved to be identical with 3-benzoylamino- β -naphthapyrone, yield 0.8 g. A further quantity (0.3 g.) was obtained by working up the coloured residue in the distilling flask.

trans α -Benzoylamino- β :2-hydroxynaphthylacrylic acid.

On acidifying the cold alkaline solution obtained by heating benzoylamino- β -naphthapyrone with 2N-alkali a reddish oil which gradually solidified separated out. It dissolved completely in cold sodium carbonate but was reprecipitated as an oil which solidified

as before and then melted rather indefinitely between 150-90°. It was purified by several crystallisations from dilute methanol as needles, m.p. 206° (decomp.). The coumarin could not be recovered from the product after melting, but the acid was converted into the coumarin both by ultraviolet illumination and by means of concentrated sulphuric acid. The acid is believed, on these grounds, to have the *trans* structure (cf. Dey and Lakshminarayanan, *loc. cit.*).

3-Amino- β -naphthapyrone.—A solution of the benzoyl compound (2 g.) in glacial acetic acid (60 c.c) was mixed with 20 c.c. of HBr (*d* 1.38) and refluxed on a sand-bath 12 hours. Most of the acetic acid was distilled off, the solution neutralised with 2*N*-ammonia and the separating solid crystallised from alcohol as clusters of needles of a cream colour, m.p. 169°, yield 0.6 g. The same compound was obtained in a much poorer yield by dissolving the benzoyl derivative in ice-cold sulphuric acid and pouring into water after 12 hours and basifying with ammonia. The amine dissolved slowly in dilute mineral acids and gave off ammonia on boiling with alkali. (Found: C, 73.7; H, 4.25; N, 6.78. $C_{13}H_9O_2N$ requires C, 73.9; H, 4.27; N, 6.63 per cent).

The *hydrochloride* was best prepared by passing HCl gas into a solution of the base in dry alcohol as colourless rectangular plates, m.p. 201°, practically insoluble in water. (Found: Cl, 14.0. $C_{13}H_{10}O_2NCl$ requires Cl, 14.3 per cent). The *sulphate* crystallised in sheaves of needles.

The *acetyl* derivative, prepared by acetylating in presence of a drop of pyridine, crystallises from alcohol in long needles, m.p. 245°. A dilute alcoholic solution shows a beautiful blue fluorescence. (Found: N, 5.67. $C_{15}H_{11}O_3N$ requires N, 5.53 per cent).

The *benzoyl* derivative, prepared in the usual way, crystallises from acetic acid in needles, m.p. 229°, not depressed by admixture with the product synthesised from hippuric acid and β -naphthol aldehyde.

3-Acetylamino- β -naphthapyrone.—A mixture of β -naphthol aldehyde (4.4 g.), glycine (2 g.), fused sodium acetate (2.2 g.) and acetic anhydride (10 g.) was heated in an oil-bath at 140° for 5 hours. The dark oil which showed no signs of solidification on leaving in the ice-chest for 24 hours was washed repeatedly with *N*/10-alkali and with 50% alcohol when it changed into a semi-solid mass. This

was dried and rubbed frequently with ether when it became granular, the ether washings being continued till no appreciable colour was removed. The resulting brownish solid was washed with hot alcohol and then crystallised twice from acetic acid (charcoal) as rosettes of cream colour needles, m.p. 245° , yield 0.7 g. It was identified as acetylamino- β -naphthapyrone by a mixed m.p. determination. On heating with HCl (1:2) for a few minutes and basifying with ammonia, the amino- β -naphthapyrone (m.p. 160°) was thrown down in a crystalline condition.

Action of alkali on 3-amino- β -naphthapyrone: cis α -Hydroxy- β :2-hydroxynaphthylacrylic acid.

The amine (1 g.) was gently boiled with *N*-alkali (8 c.c.) till NH_3 ceased to evolve. The solution which assumed a golden yellow colour was cooled in ice, neutralised with HCl and the sticky mass, which became granular on standing, purified by dissolving in sodium carbonate and reprecipitation. It crystallised from hot water in plates which sintered at 120° and melted completely at 136° (decomp.). The residue after melting solidified. It was then found to melt at $215\text{--}20^{\circ}$. (Found: M.W., 226. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4$ requires M.W., 230).

3-Hydroxy- β -naphthapyrone.—The acid obtained by heating the amino- β -naphthapyrone with alkali was heated at 160° for 10 minutes; the acid melted to a colourless liquid with the evolution of steam and resolidified. It was crystallised from dilute methanol as greenish needles, m.p., 230° , soluble in alkali but insoluble in carbonate. It gave an inky colour with neutral ferric chloride. (Found: C, 73.02; H, 3.80. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_8\text{O}_3$ requires C, 73.58; H, 3.7 per cent).

3-Acetoxy- β -naphthapyrone crystallised from alcohol in micaceous plates, m.p. 162° . The crystals themselves exhibited a light blue fluorescence and the solution in alcohol fluoresced powerfully.

(Found: C, 70.3 ; H, 4.1. $C_{15}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 70.9; H, 4.0 per cent). The *benzoyl* derivative melted at 172°.

Action of nitrous acid on amino- β -naphthapyrone.—To a solution of the amine (0.8 g.) in methanol containing 4N-HCl (4 c.c) a solution of sodium nitrite (0.5 g.) was run in drop by drop. The green precipitate was filtered and treated with very dilute alkali when a portion of it dissolved to a deep red solution. The insoluble residue was found to be unchanged amine. The alkaline solution on acidification precipitated brown solid which crystallised from alcohol (charcoal) in needles, m.p. 228°, not lowered by admixture with 3-hydroxynaphthapyrone, m.p. 230°.

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